

Aysegul Ilgaz (2024): Balancing Autonomy and Protection: Ethical and Privacy Issues in Active and Assisted Living Technologies for Older People. In: Proceedings of the Joint visuAAL-GoodBrother Conference on trustworthy video- and audio-based assistive technologies – COST Action CA19121 - Network on Privacy-Aware Audio- and Video-Based Applications for Active and Assisted Living

Balancing Autonomy and Protection: Ethical and Privacy Issues in Active and Assisted Living Technologies for Older People

Aysegul Ilgaz

Akdeniz University Faculty of Nursing, Department of Public Health Nursing
aozer2012@gmail.com

Abstract

Elderly people's life can be significantly enhanced by active and assistive living (AALs) technologies. With the goal of enhancing older people's quality of life and lessening the load on caregivers, AALs technologies encompass any gadget that supports the psychological and physiological changes that come with age. There is a growing discourse over the potential of technological methods to facilitate assistance with everyday tasks. One common argument for AALs technologies is that they help people become more autonomous. A person's autonomy isn't always reduced just because they utilize an assistive gadget. Including senior citizens in decision-making on a regular basis may guarantee that AALs are viewed as an important instrument to support senior citizens' independence and autonomy. And also, the rights to personal data protection (privacy), as well as the rights and inclusion of older people, are major issues. Security and privacy issues are brought up by the fact that AALs technologies frequently gather sensitive personal data in

order to operate. It is vital to guarantee that these gadgets follow stringent privacy regulations and utilize strong security protocols to safeguard user information.

It is assumed that all AALs technologies have both positive and negative effects on the circumstances of how environments function, which may have a vital impact on people's health and quality of life. These technologies are touted for their alleged benefits. Nevertheless, privacy concerns and ethical standards are disregarded in its utilization. It is necessary to consider the ethical principles such as autonomy, non-maleficence, beneficence, fairness, interdependence, and privacy. Devices that support personal autonomy include new AALs technologies that can be used to track routine daily patterns or capture physiological data. In order to balance autonomy and protection, this study explores the ethical and privacy concerns related to the use of AALs technologies in depth, underline these issues in detail from an ethical perspective, and offer potential recommendations.

References

- Martin, S., Bengtsson, J.E., Dröes, R.M. (2010). Assistive Technologies and Issues Relating to Privacy, Ethics and Security. In: Mulvenna, M., Nugent, C. (eds) Supporting People with Dementia Using Pervasive Health Technologies. Advanced Information and Knowledge Processing. Springer, London, pp. 63-76.
- Morte, Ricardo., Toboso, Mario., Aparicio, Manuel., Ausín, Txetxu., Monasterio, Aníbal., López, Daniel. (2020). Personal autonomy in elderly and disabled: How assistive technologies impact on it". *Aging between Participation and Simulation: Ethical Dimensions of Socially Assistive Technologies in Elderly Care*, edited by Joschka Haltaufderheide, Johanna Hovemann and Jochen Vollmann, Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, pp. 185-198.
- Schicktanz, S., Schweda, M. (2021). Aging 4.0? Rethinking the ethical framing of technology-assisted eldercare. *HPLS*, vol. 43, no. 93, pp. 1-19.
- Wangmo, T., Lipps, M., Kressig, R. W., & Ienca, M. (2019). Ethical concerns with the use of intelligent assistive technology: findings from a qualitative study with professional stakeholders. *BMC Medical Ethics*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 98.